

Acute Nicotine Exposure Impairs Glucose Metabolism in Male Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Clinical and experimental reports on insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism following nicotine exposure remain contradictory. The implications of acute exposure to nicotine on glucose metabolism were therefore studied in male Wistar rats.

Male Wistar rats (250-300g) were grouped into three (n=12) as control (administered normal saline), 50µg/Kg Nicotine-treated (Nic-50) and 100µg/Kg Nicotine-treated (Nic-100). Intraperitoneal administrations of normal saline or nicotine was done 30 minutes before loading the rats with glucose (2g/kg) for oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT). Liver and gastrocnemius muscle samples were obtained after 30 minutes (n=6) and 90 minutes (n=6) of glucose load in each group corresponding to the peak of glucose appearance and decline in the blood during the OGTT. Glucose disposal was obtained from the Area Under the Curve (AUC). Plasma insulin, adrenaline, hepatic cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), Liver and muscle glycogen concentration and Glycogen Phosphorylase (GP) and Synthase (GS) activities were determined.

Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG) (mg/dL) and AUC (mg/dL*min) significantly increased in Nic-50 (93.30±8.88 and 21689.00±956.62) and Nic-100 (94.33±5.41 and 23697.00±1070.77). The AUC insulin significantly increased, while hepatic cAMP significantly decreased at 30 and 90 minutes. Hepatic glycogen significantly increased at 30 minutes in Nic-50 and Nic-100 but decreased at 90 minutes in Nic-100. Muscle glycogen significantly increased in Nic-50 and Nic-100 at 30 minutes but decreased at 90 minutes. Liver and muscle GS activities significantly increased at 30 minutes, while liver GS significantly reduced at 90 minutes in Nic-100. Liver and muscle GP activities significantly reduced at 30 minutes, while liver GP significantly increased in Nic-100 at 90 minutes.

It was concluded that acute nicotine exposure caused glucose-intolerance arising from impaired glucose uptake in male Wistar rats.

Keywords: Nicotine, Acute exposure, Glucose intolerance, Insulin resistance

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Introduction

Nicotine, an alkaloid compound contained majorly in plants belonging to the Solanaceae family (Doolittle et al., 1995; Siddiqui and Jaimes, 2016), is widely used around the world. It is mainly consumed through tobacco products like cigarettes, cigars, and snuff. However, it is also contained in commonly eaten foods such as tomatoes, peppers, and eggplant. Nicotine is the active substance in tobacco believed to be responsible for its effects. Eight million people have been estimated to die of tobacco use yearly, with approximately 1.3 millions of these deaths

attributed to secondhand smoke (Reitsma et al., 2021; WHO, 2023). In Nigeria, the prevalence of cigarette smoking is about 10.4% (Adeloye et al., 2019), meaning that roughly one out of every ten people in the country is exposed to this drug. Nicotine delivery systems have been advanced to include electronic means such as vape pens, e-pipes, e-cigars and e-cigarettes, which have gained global popularity, especially among the youth. E-cigarette is the most common of these systems, often resembling traditional cigarettes in appearance (Stefaniak et al., 2021), and can deliver nicotine concentrations comparable to

traditional cigarettes. In Nigeria, the use and projected revenue from e-cigarettes in 2025 are estimated to reach \$181.4 million (Statista, 2025). This presents a significant public health concern.

As a substance of interest, nicotine is reported to be well-tolerated by the body with repeated and prolonged exposure (Wang and Sun, 2005; Aslam et al., 2024). Nicotine causes a wide range of effects, including a reduction in body weight (Stadler et al., 2014; Shankar et al., 2024), decreased fertility (Oyeyipo et al., 2013; Firouzabadi et al., 2025), impaired immune response (Mahmoudzadeh et al., 2023), and increased cardiovascular responses: mean pulse rate, blood pressure and heart rate (Price and Martinez, 2020). Numerous reports on nicotine impact on metabolism of carbohydrate have been published; however, these studies have been inconsistent and conflicting. For instance, Alada (2001), Oyebola et al. (2009) and Vu et al. (2014) reported that nicotine causes a rise in blood glucose, while Grunberg et al. (1988) and Xu et al. (2012) documented no impact of nicotine on blood glucose level. In smokers and Type 2 diabetic patients, impaired sensitivity to insulin had been documented following nicotine administration while insulin sensitivity is intact in normoglycemic participants (Axelsson et al., 2001; Morgan et al., 2004). Another study did not identify any relationship between nicotine exposure and glucose tolerance in participants with diabetes mellitus (Epifano et al., 1992). Nicotine pellets implanted subcutaneously in adult and juvenile rats did not affect insulin sensitivity (Swislocki et al., 1997; Swislocki, 2003), whereas quitting smoking led to an improvement in insulin sensitivity (Eliasson et al., 1997).

There are several discrepancies in these findings, which could be attributed to factors such as the route, dosage and, duration of nicotine treatment as well as the species of the animal model. The difference in the outcomes of nicotine exposure on insulin sensitivity cannot however be explained totally by these factors. There is therefore a need for further studies to provide answers to a number of questions that have emerged with respect to insulin sensitivity following nicotine exposure in different animal models. Additionally, studies involving humans may have other extraneous factors beyond those in animal studies. There are over 7000 compounds in tobacco smoke (WHO, 2019); hence, nicotine may not be the only active substance mediating the effects

associated with tobacco or its products. There may also be individual differences and under-reporting in the self-report of recruited subjects in clinical studies on their smoking history with regards to the number and bioavailability of tobacco products consumed (Volk et al., 2020) and how it was consumed over a period of time (Liber and Warner, 2018; Volk et al., 2020). With regards to the discrepancies in the reported nicotine activities on the metabolism of glucose in animals and humans, there is a need for further investigation.

The current study aimed to investigate the effects of acute exposure to nicotine on glucose metabolism and sensitivity to insulin using male Wistar rats. Specifically, this study examined the effect of acute nicotine exposure on glucose tolerance, fasting blood glucose level, insulin, adrenaline, hepatic cyclic AMP, liver and muscle glycogen content, glycogen phosphorylase and glycogen synthase activities in male Wistar rats.

Material and methods

Animals: Thirty-six male rats of Wistar strain (250 – 300 g) kept in the postgraduate research animal house of Physiology Department, University of Ibadan, Nigeria were used. They were maintained in standard laboratory conditions (12/12-hour light/dark cycle) with access to water and standard rat feed (Ladokun® feeds) *ad libitum*. Following two weeks of acclimatization, the animals were grouped into 3 (n=12) as control administered normal saline, 50µg/Kg Nicotine treated (Nic-50) and 100µg/Kg Nicotine treated (Nic-100). The protocol for this experiment received institutional ethical approval (UI-ACUREC/084-1021/06).

Methods: After an overnight fast, basal blood sample was taken for glucose measurement. Thereafter, normal saline or nicotine was intraperitoneally administered 30 minutes before commencement of OGTT. Blood samplings were done serially at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 150 minutes from the rat tail vein to determine blood glucose and from the retro-orbital sinus for the determination of insulin and adrenaline levels.

At 30 minutes and 90 minutes which correspond to the peak and decline of glucose appearance in the blood during the OGTT, 6 rats in each group were euthanized by cervical dislocation and the liver and gastrocnemius muscle were obtained to determine glycogen levels and activities of glycogen phosphorylase

and glycogen synthase enzymes. cyclic AMP levels were also determined in the liver.

Oral Glucose Tolerance Test: Following an overnight fast, a basal blood sample was collected to determine basal blood glucose. Thereafter, they were orally loaded 2g/kg of glucose (Xu et al., 2012). Then blood samples were collected serially at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 150 minutes from the rat tail vein for determination of blood glucose using a portable Accu-Chek Active© blood glucometer (Roche Diagnostics, Germany).

Plasma Insulin and Adrenaline determination: Blood samples (0.5ml) obtained from the animal were collected in an Eppendorf tube containing 50µL EDTA and centrifuged at 3000 rev/min for 5 minutes. Plasma was then extracted into sterile cryogenic vials and stored at -20 °C for assay. Plasma insulin was assayed using Calbiotech® Insulin ELISA kit while Adrenaline concentration was determined using the Bioassay Technology Laboratory® ELISA kit according to the manufacturers' instructions.

Glycogen determination: Determination of hepatic and gastrocnemius muscle glycogen content was based on Seifter et al. (1950) and Jermyn (1975) method as described by Shittu et al. (2018). Briefly, 1g of tissue was solubilized in KOH and washed in ethanol to obtain a white precipitate after centrifugation. The precipitate was reconstituted in distilled water. Equal volumes (500 µL) of the reconstituted precipitate, Conc HCl, and formic acid added step wisely followed by 4ml of Anthrone reagent. Serial dilutions of 0.2 mg/ml of glycogen standard were done and treated similarly. They were incubated at 100 °C for 10 minutes and read against reagent blank when cooled at 630 nm.

Cyclic AMP determination: Liver samples obtained from the animals were homogenised on ice in 5ml of 0.1N hydrochloric acid. The homogenate was centrifuged using cold centrifuge (Eppendorf c20) for 5 minutes and the supernatant extracted into cryogenic vials and stored at -20°C for assay. Concentration of liver cAMP was determined using Biovision Incorporated® ELISA kit according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Glycogen Synthase and Phosphorylase determination: Liver and gastrocnemius muscle samples obtained from the animal were

rinsed in 1.15% potassium chloride and dried on filter paper. Samples were homogenised on ice in Phosphate buffer Saline (pH7.4). The homogenate was centrifuged using cold centrifuge (Eppendorf c20) and the supernatant obtained and stored at -20°C for enzyme determination.

The method described by Danforth (1965) was used to assay glycogen synthase activity. Tissue supernatants (100µl) were individually pipetted into tubes containing reaction cocktail [Constituent: MgCl₂, β-Mercaptoethanol, EDTA-tetrasodium UDPG, Tris HCl buffer (pH 8.2), glycogen and deionized water], mixed, incubated at 30°C for 5 minutes. Thereafter, it was heated for 5minutes at 100°C, cooled under running water and centrifuged. One hundred microliter was then added to another tube containing KCl, β-NADH, Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.5), EDTA-tetrasodium, MgSO₄, Phosphoenol pyruvate, PK/LDH enzyme and deionized water. The mixture was immediately introduced into cuvette and change in absorbance was monitored for 5 minutes at 340 nm.

The method of Bergmeyer et al. (1974) was employed to assay glycogen phosphorylase activity. Briefly, 100µl of the tissue supernatant in the absence of 5'-AMP was added to a reaction [constituent: MgCl₂, glycogen, EDTA, phosphoglucomutase, NADPH and Potassium Phosphate buffer]. It was mixed and transferred into cuvette, the changes in absorbance over 10 minutes was obtained at 340 nm.

Data Analysis: Data collected were presented as mean±standard error of mean (SEM), Inferential statistic was done ANOVA followed by Games-Howell post hoc test at p≤0.05 with the aid of GraphPad Prism® version 8.0.

Results

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on fasting blood glucose level: As shown in figure 1, fasting blood glucose level was significantly (P < 0.05) increased in Nic-50 (93.30 ± 8.88 mg/dl) and Nic-100 (94.33 ± 5.41 mg/dl) groups following nicotine exposure when compared with the control (77.75 ± 0.99 mg/dl).

Fig 1: Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on fasting blood glucose in male Wistar rats. (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on glucose tolerance and insulin response: The disposal of glucose was significantly reduced in the Nic-50 and Nic-100 groups with respect to the control, as shown by the significantly increased blood glucose during the OGTT (Figure 2A). The increased blood glucose reached its peak at the 30th minute and thereafter decreased to a plateau at 90 minutes before returning to the basal level. As shown in figure 2B, the area under the curve of the OGTT was significantly increased by nicotine treatment with higher dose of nicotine (100 μ g/Kg) producing a more significant effect than 50 μ g/Kg. Figure 2C shows the area under the curve of the insulin levels plotted against time, it indicates the response by insulin secretion to the glucose load. Acute administration of nicotine significantly increased plasma insulin levels in both Nic-50 and Nic-100 when compared with the control. The effects produced by the two doses were however not significantly different.

A

B

C

Fig 2: Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on (A) glucose level, area under the curve of (B) glucose response and (C) insulin response after glucose loading over time in male Wistar rats. (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on plasma adrenaline level: As shown in figure 3A, there

was significant reduction in plasma adrenaline level in Nic-50 group when compared with

control 30 minutes post injection. Although an apparent decrease was observed in Nic-100 as well, it was not statistically different from control. At 90 minutes post administration, the

effect had diminished in the two treated groups (Figure 3B).

Fig 3: Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on Plasma adrenaline levels at (A) 30 minutes and (B) 90 minutes post administration in male Wistar rats (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on cAMP levels: Hepatic cAMP level was significantly reduced at 30 minutes post administration of nicotine (Figure 4A). This reduction was more pronounced in the nicotine 50 μ g/Kg treated

group compared with nicotine 100 μ g/Kg treated group. At 90 minutes post administration, the reduction in cAMP persisted (Figure 4B). The effects produced by the two doses were however not significantly different

Fig 4: Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on liver cAMP levels at (A) 30 minutes and (B) 90 minutes post administration in male Wistar rats (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on liver glycogen content: At 30 minutes post administration, nicotine caused an increase in liver glycogen content. However, this increase was only significant in Nic-100 group when

compared with control (Figure 5A). At the 90th minute, nicotine produced a significant decrease in liver glycogen content of the Nic-100 group when compared with both the control and Nic-50 group (Figure 5B).

Fig 5: Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on liver glycogen at (A) 30 minutes and (B) 90 minutes post administration in male Wistar rats (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control, # $P < 0.5$ Vs Nic-50).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on the gastrocnemius muscle glycogen content: The gastrocnemius muscle glycogen content increased significantly at 30 minutes post-

administration of nicotine in Nic-50 and Nic-100 groups. However, at 90 minutes post-injection, the effect had diminished in the two treated groups (Figure 6 A and B).

Fig 6. Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on Muscle glycogen at (A) 30 minutes and (B) 90 minutes post administration in male Wistar rats (* $p < 0.05$ Vs control).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on hepatic Glycogen Synthase Activity: Hepatic glycogen synthase activity was significantly increased at 30 minutes post administration of nicotine. This increase persisted in the 50 μ g/Kg treated group with respect to control and the 100 μ g/Kg treated group 90minutes post nicotine administration (Table 1).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on Muscle Glycogen Synthase Activity: Activities of gastrocnemius muscle glycogen synthase were increased significantly in the two nicotine-treated groups at 30 minutes post administration of nicotine. This effect was no longer significant 90 minutes post administration (Table 1).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on hepatic Glycogen Phosphorylase Activity: There was a significant decrease in the glycogen phosphorylase activity in the liver 30 minutes post administration of nicotine. This increase persisted in the Nic-50 group when compared with control and the Nic-100 group 90 minutes post administration (Table 1).

Effect of acute nicotine exposure on Muscle Glycogen Phosphorylase Activity: Muscle glycogen phosphorylase activity decreased significantly at 30 minutes post administration of nicotine in both Nic-50 and Nic-100. However, the observed reduction diminished by the 90th minute (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of acute administration of Nicotine on hepatic and gastrocnemius muscle glycogen synthase and phosphorylase activities in male Wistar rats

Tissue	Enzyme	Time	Control	Nic-50	Nic-100
Liver	Glycogen Synthase	30 mins	3.76± 0.26	5.43± 0.31*	6.88± 0.39*
		90 mins	3.76± 0.26	5.96± 0.37*	3.78± 0.23 [#]
	Glycogen Phosphorylase	30 mins	87.81± 4.06	67.82± 6.63*	47.84± 5.62* [#]
		90 mins	87.81± 4.06	50.80± 2.27*	98.55± 10.76 [#]
Muscle	Glycogen Synthase	30 mins	4.53±0.36	6.60± 0.63*	7.88± 0.57
		90 mins	4.53±0.36	5.22± 0.36	4.95± 0.61
	Glycogen Phosphorylase	30 mins	92.19± 4.53	58.28± 6.31*	41.02± 4.73 [#]
		90 mins	92.19± 4.53	82.08± 8.20	88.52± 6.26

(*p<0.05 Vs control, [#]p<0.05 Nic-50 Vs Nic-100).

Discussion

Nicotine, a major bioactive component of tobacco, is widely researched for its pharmacological activities in various physiological systems, including metabolism and endocrine function. The observed elevation in fasting blood glucose levels after acute administration of nicotine in the current study is in line with earlier reports on the effects of nicotine (Tsujimoto et al., 1965; Milton, 1966; Sanberg et al., 1973; Grayson and Oyebola, 1985; Alada, 2001).

The observed increase in glucose intolerance is in consistence with earlier reports (Houston et al., 2006; Vu et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2023). The delayed glucose disposal observed could be attributed to reduced insulin sensitivity (Fрати et al., 1996) and impaired glucose uptake by peripheral tissues (Attval et al., 1993). The data in this study supported the findings by Vu et al. (2014). Vu and colleagues, in the acute phase of their experiment, administered an oral glucose load (1 mg/g body weight, intraperitoneally) to normal (insulin-sensitive) animals 30 minutes after administering nicotine intraperitoneally and reported an increase in blood glucose and glucose intolerance. However, they administered a nicotine dose of 0.2 µg/g (equivalent to 200 µg/Kg), which is times 2 and 4, respectively of the 50 µg/Kg and 100 µg/Kg used in the current study.

The increased level of insulin following the acute administration of nicotine is a consequence of the high blood glucose levels induced by nicotine administration (Milton, 1966; Alada, 2001; Vu et al., 2014). Typically, insulin is released in response to elevated blood glucose levels, which is part of the homeostatic process that regulates blood glucose levels. The sustained elevated plasma insulin levels observed in the present study could be a homeostatic response to the elevated blood

glucose and a natural reaction to counteract the high blood glucose levels induced by the nicotine administration. Vu and colleagues also reported increased plasma insulin post-nicotine exposure in the acute phase of their study in wild-type mice that were administered nicotine 0.2µg/g, followed by a glucose challenge (1mg/g) 30 minutes after the nicotine treatment. Though in their study, the 0.2µg/g administered (equivalent to 200µg/Kg) dose of nicotine was far higher than the doses (50µg/Kg and 100µg/Kg) used in the current study.

The decrease in adrenaline levels as a result of acute nicotine administration in this study was unexpected, given that nicotine is established to act via the release of adrenaline to mediate its effects (Tsujimoto et al., 1965; Milton, 1966; Oyebola and Alada, 1993). The observed decrease in adrenaline levels probably suggests that adrenaline may not be involved in the nicotine-induced hyperglycemia in this study. This differed from the study of Vu et al. (2014), who reported an increase in adrenaline levels 30 minutes post administration of nicotine. However, in their research, a higher dose of nicotine was administered (0.2µg/g) (200µg/Kg). This finding suggests that the effects of the significantly higher dose may not be directly comparable to those seen with the lower dose employed in this study. The observed decrease in cyclic AMP following acute nicotine administration correlates with the reduction in adrenaline observed in this study. Cyclic AMP is an essential second messenger in cellular metabolism.

The observed increase in glycogen following nicotine administration likely suggests that the excess glucose in the blood was converted to glycogen within the 30 minutes post-injection. However, the observed reduction in the effect of the nicotine on glycogen at 90 minutes

probably indicates that nicotine may be producing a different effect. This is consistent with some earlier reports of the action of nicotine. For instance, nicotine at low dose is known to be a ganglion stimulant and at high dose, it is a ganglion inhibitor (Marks et al., 1983). It is thus not out of place to conclude that nicotine could probably elicit different actions at different doses and at different durations (Marks et al., 1983) with regards to glycogen contents. The increased activities of GS and reduction in GP activity are consistent with their well-known functions (Shittu et al., 2018; 2020). Glycogen synthase catalyses the incorporation of glucose units cleaved from uridine diphosphate-glucose to the glycogen chain and thus is a rate-limiting enzyme in glycogenesis. There is a reverse relationship between GS and GP, activation of GP correlates with an inhibition of GS (Shittu et al., 2020). In the present study, the inverse relationship between glycogen synthase and glycogen phosphorylase reflected on the glycogen content in both the muscle and liver. In other words, glycogen contents decreases when synthase activities decreased and phosphorylase activity increased.

Conclusion: This study reveals that acute exposure to nicotine results in reduced glucose tolerance and increased insulin resistance in a dose-dependent manner; however, this effect is not attributed to the action of catecholamines.

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